

Unusual co-occurrence of *Prorocentrum lima* and *P. rhathymum* in a mucilaginous river plume in a tropical Atlantic estuary (northeast Brazil)

Prorocentrum is a morphologically distinctive genus of desmokyont dinoflagellates found in both planktonic and benthic environments. This genus has a broad geographic distribution and play an important role in marine trophic dynamics [1–2]. Epiphytic species of *Prorocentrum* are frequently found in shallow tropical waters, attached to substrates such as macroalgae, coral reefs, and sediments by producing mucous polysaccharide filaments [3]. Despite their benthic distribution, these species have flagella and can get detached, transitioning into a planktonic form during part of their vegetative cycle [4]. Warm water temperatures typically enhance their growth and distribution, especially in tropical regions [4], where the response of biological communities to increasing temperature remains an open question with high relevance in global climate change projections [5].

In recent decades, there has been a considerable numerical increase in reports about the intensification of toxic or harmful algal blooms (HABs), with implications for ecological balance and human health [6]. Although HABs are most commonly associated with planktonic species, benthic species may

cause Benthic Harmful Algal Blooms (BHABs) [7]. These noxious blooms occur when toxigenic dinoflagellates are transferred through the food web, leading to shellfish poisoning events that affect marine fauna (including vertebrates) and humans. In addition, some species may reach high cell densities and release toxins in the seawater and the atmosphere, which can cause skin irritation and breathing difficulties in sunbathers. Among the toxigenic benthic dinoflagellates, *Prorocentrum lima* and *Prorocentrum rhathymum* are well-known species of concern. *P. lima* has been linked to diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP) outbreaks in several regions [8], while *P. rhathymum*, a tycho planktonic species previously identified as *P. mexicanum*, has been associated with red tide (discolouration) events in tropical systems [9]. On tropical and subtropical Atlantic coasts, both species have been documented as contributors to toxin-related events. In Brazilian waters, *P. lima* has been reported from latitudes 8°S to 27°S, consistently appearing attached to macroalgae [7], but most studies have focused on cultures or epiphyte collections, with limited understanding of the ecology

and behaviour of field populations.

During a field survey on 3 September 2021, a yellow-brownish foam with a greasy appearance was observed in a river plume at the upstream section of the Serinhaém River, within Camamu Bay, Bahia, Brazil (13°43'38.8"S; 39°08'04.0"W) (Fig. 1). This plume measured approximately eight meters long and one meter wide (Fig. 2). This estuarine region, surrounded by protected mangrove and Atlantic Forest vegetation ("mata Atlântica"), supports artisanal fisheries and tourism. A sample of the foam was manually collected in a plastic container without preservatives and immediately cooled for transport. Environmental variables including temperature, pH, depth, and salinity were recorded in situ using standard multiparameter probes and equipment. Water transparency was measured using a Secchi disk. Samples for nutrient analysis were cooled and frozen for spectrophotometric analysis following established protocols [10]. Light microscopic observation of the foam aggregates revealed a mixture of several *Prorocentrum* species (Fig. 3). Cell counts were estimated according to the Utermöhl method, with 2 mL of homogenized sample analyzed under an inverted microscope at 400× magnification. Thirty random transects were examined and extrapolated to estimate total concentrations. The estimated cell concentrations were 2.04×10^6 cells·L⁻¹ for *P. rhathymum* and 1.69×10^6 cells·L⁻¹ for the *P. lima* complex. Cells were well preserved, with visible chloroplasts,

Fig. 1. (A) Geographic location of the Serinhaém River estuary in the State of Bahia, Brazil (X indicates the site where the bloom was observed). (B) Zoomed view showing the urban occupation of Ituberá along the river margins near the sampling site.

Fig. 2. A) Field photograph of the surface foam plume observed on 3 September 2021; B) Close-up photograph of the foam, highlighting its greasy, yellow-brownish mucilaginous texture.

starch sheaths, mucocysts, and pyrenoids. Some empty thecae were observed. Taxonomic identification was confirmed using scanning electron microscopy after dehydration and critical point drying. Morphological criteria for species identification included periflagellar platelets, anterior spines, trichocyst pore arrangements, and overall dimensions [2]. *P. rathymum* displayed reticulated-foveate surface ornamentation and pore lines radiating from a central point. Cells were elliptical or oblong, with plates measuring 36–42 μm in length and 24–30 μm in width,

with a length-to-width ratio of approximately 1.4. The *P. lima* complex exhibited kidney-shaped pores and a smaller length-to-width ratio (1.25–2.35), with plate sizes of 36–42 μm in length and 17–33 μm in width. Images showed multiple cells aggregated and embedded in mucilage, possibly indicating in situ aggregation. Light microscopy further revealed chloroplasts and starch rings in both species (Fig. 4).

At the time of sampling, the water temperature was 25.3 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, salinity 15.6, pH 6.58, and river depth was 11.6 m. The concentrations of total phosphorus,

total nitrogen, and phosphate were 1.30 $\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, 19.6 $\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, and 0.3 $\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively. These nutrient levels suggest nitrogen enrichment and phosphorus limitation—conditions often associated with eutrophication and anthropogenic impact in estuarine environments [6–7]. The estimated N:P ratio at the bloom site exceeded 100:1, a significant indicator of potential ecological imbalance. Similar high N:P ratios have been in other systems have been interpreted as signs of phosphorus limitation, especially in the freshwater sections of estuaries where nitrogen

Fig. 3. Light micrograph (10 \times magnification) of the collected foam sample, illustrating the dense particulate (right) and cellular matter (left) and a zoomed view of an aggregation of *Prorocentrum lima* complex and *Prorocentrum rathymum* cells within the sample debris.

Fig. 4. Scanning electron micrograph showing dinoflagellate specimens aggregated onto a macroalgal debris fragment (left) and light micrograph displaying *P. lima* complex and *P. rathymum* side-by-side within the fixed sample slide, with visible features such as chloroplasts, nuclei, anterior spine, periflagellar platelets, starch ring, and trichocysts (right).

often dominates [6]. The measured environmental conditions—nutrient availability, light penetration, and reduced turbulence—are conducive to HAB formation [6]. Tropical temperatures may further favour *Prorocentrum* proliferation [4], while low turbulence in upstream estuarine zones may facilitate mucilaginous aggregations that appear as surface foam.

The bloom occurred adjacent to urban areas with low levels of sewage treatment—only 36% of domestic waste is treated in Ituberá—suggesting anthropogenic nutrient input [11]. While causality cannot be firmly established, the Brazilian demographic census reported 4.6 diarrhoea-related hospital admissions per 1,000 residents in this region, which is consistent with DSP symptomatology [7].

A broader environmental characterization of the Serinhaém River estuary, including areas without such foam plumes, is provided by Noga et al (2025) [11]. That study offer additional insight into the estuary's hydrology, nutrient gradients, anthropogenic pressures, and spatial heterogeneity relevant to interpreting the bloom described herein. To the best of our knowledge, this bloom is the first of its kind recorded in Atlantic waters. Only one other bloom of *P. rathymum* with similar characteristics has been reported—in the Bangaram lagoon,

India—where similar yellow-brownish mucilaginous foams were observed [9]. The resemblance in colour, texture, and species composition suggests that such blooms may occur in other tropical systems under similar environmental conditions. This event is of particular concern given the local reliance on fish and shellfish for subsistence and commerce. The presence of high concentrations of *P. lima* and *P. rathymum*—two toxigenic species—highlights the need for monitoring, particularly in regions lacking HAB surveillance. The co-occurrence of these species in a free-floating, bloom-forming state is unprecedented in this region and contributes to our understanding of their ecological plasticity. Their ability to shift to a planktonic state, especially in eutrophic tropical estuaries, expands the risk they pose to ecosystem health and human populations. With ongoing coastal urbanization and rising temperatures, such events may become more frequent.

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